

RESEARCH ARTICLE

 OPEN ACCESS

Received: 03-06-2024

Accepted: 29-07-2024

Published: 30-08-2024

Citation: Muthukrishnan R, James CK (2024) The Effect of Multicollinearity on Feature Selection. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 17(35): 3664-3668. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v17i35.1876>

* **Corresponding author.**jamesck74@gmail.com**Funding:** None**Competing Interests:** None

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Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](#))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

The Effect of Multicollinearity on Feature Selection

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Abstract

Objectives: To provide a new LASSO-based feature selection technique that aids in selecting important variables for predicting the response variables in case of multicollinearity. **Methods:** LASSO is a type of regression method employed to select important covariates for predicting a dependent variable. The traditional LASSO method uses the conventional Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method for this purpose. The Use of the OLS based LASSO approach gives unreliable results if the data deviates from normality. Thus, this study recommends using, a Redescending M-estimator-based LASSO approach. The efficacy of this new method is checked against the ordinary LASSO method using a real dataset and also a simulation study with various levels of sample size (N=100,200,1000), different numbers of predictors ($p=10,15,20$), and varying degrees of correlation ($\rho = 0.96, 0.98, 0.999$). **Findings:** The usual OLS-based LASSO finds it difficult to select important variables when the independent variables are correlated. The Redescending M-estimator-based LASSO addresses at tackling the pitfalls faced by Conventional LASSO methodology. Among other things, the proposed method is far better than the old-fashioned LASSO since it helps to pick out significant factors more effectively, particularly in the presence of multicollinearity. **Novelty:** The conventional OLS-based LASSO approach selects a greater number of non-significant variables in the presence of multicollinearity. The proposed Redescending M-estimator-based LASSO approach selects the important variables in the presence of multicollinearity.

Keywords: Feature Selection; LASSO; MDAE; VIF; Variable Selection

1 Introduction

Regression analysis involves forecasting a dependent variable through the use of one or more independent variables⁽¹⁾. It aims to understand how a dependent variable changes when the independent variables vary. A popular regression technique, called Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO), was developed by Tibshirani⁽²⁾ and chooses the predictor variables that are necessary for the prediction of a response. The main disadvantage of LASSO is its reliance on OLS. OLS-based approaches are highly affected by outliers in the dataset as they can give biased results.

To overcome this, some robust-based LASSO approaches for feature selection methods have been introduced in the literature. LAD-LASSO⁽³⁾ and Huber-LASSO⁽⁴⁾ are some of the robust methods that help to deal with the problem of outliers. The other main challenge in LASSO regression is the presence of multicollinearity. Frisch⁽⁵⁾ was the first person to bring out the concept of multicollinearity. Multicollinearity means that there is no orthogonality among predictor variables in a model. Nonetheless, near multicollinearity, which implies almost linear dependence, is also believed to be problematic from a statistical perspective⁽⁶⁾. High correlations among independent variables result in persistently fluctuating and exaggerated standard errors. Traditional approaches can be affected by this, leading to parameter estimation bias and inaccurate predictions. Numerous techniques have been proposed in the literature to address substantial multicollinearity. Muthukrishnan and Karthika⁽⁷⁾ studied the effect of multicollinearity and outlier in classical and robust estimators. Jinse and Varadharajan⁽⁸⁾ used a different approach in dealing the multicollinearity.

When dealing with a greater number of variables, selecting the important ones can be difficult. The method suggested by Tibshirani⁽²⁾ helps in selecting the important variable. It is also mentioned that LASSO is based on the OLS approach, so, it gives unreliable results if the data deviates from normality. The other methods developed by different authors to deal with the problem of multicollinearity do not help with feature selection. Chan et al.,⁽⁹⁾ used a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) based approach in selecting the variables. Kyriazos and Poga⁽¹⁰⁾ provide some ideas to deal with Multicollinearity in factor analysis. In this paper, a new robust-based feature selection method has been introduced to overcome the problems faced by the traditional LASSO method and focuses on the accuracy and reliability of variable selection. While ordinary LASSO tends to retain many highly correlated variables, potentially leading to overfitting and less interpretable models, our method selectively identifies all significant variables, thus providing clearer insights into the underlying data structure. This new method not only improves the model prediction but also selects the most important variable in the presence of multicollinearity. Simulation and a real-data study have been carried out to check the efficiency of selecting the important variables using the proposed method when comparing it with the ordinary LASSO method.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides a brief introduction to the methodology of LASSO and the proposed Alarm Weight-LASSO (AW-LASSO) method. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is described in Section 3. Real and simulation study is conducted to check the performance of the proposed method in section 4. Finally, Section 5 gives a summary and conclusion.

2 Methodology

The primary goal is to enhance model interpretability and variable selection, recognizing that prediction accuracy is a crucial aspect of model performance. The proposed method specifically addresses issues of variable selection and model interpretability, which are often compromised by multicollinearity. By effectively identifying and selecting significant variables, the method ensures that the model remains interpretable and the selected predictors are meaningful, without sacrificing predictive accuracy. In this section, we discuss the ordinary method used for feature selection and introduce the proposed method and its procedure.

2.1 LASSO

The LASSO method plays a critical role in the feature selection process. It is a popular technique used in statistics and machine learning for feature selection and regularization. It is well-known for its ability to select a subset of variables from a larger set. This encourages sparse solutions, wherein only a subset of predictors is considered significant. Such functionality is particularly advantageous in scenarios with high-dimensional datasets. The LASSO method minimizes the following objective function

$$\beta_{LASSO} = \min_{\beta} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \left(y_i - \sum_j \beta_j X_{ij} \right)^2 + \lambda \sum_j |\beta_j| \right) \quad (1)$$

In the above equation where y represents the dependent variable, X is the matrix of independent variables, and β is the vector of coefficients to be estimated. The regularization strength in LASSO is controlled by the parameter λ , which is non-negative. λ determines the degree of shrinkage applied to the coefficients, with higher values leading to more coefficients being set to zero, resulting in a simpler model with fewer predictors. Selecting the optimal λ value is critical because it leads to overfitting and underfitting. Cross-validation is a commonly used technique to choose the best λ value by evaluating the model's performance on different subsets of the data. This helps in selecting a λ value that balances model complexity and predictive power effectively.

2.2 Robust LASSO Approach

Consider Equation (1), which combines the Residual sum of Squares (RSS) with a penalty function. OLS-based approaches are known to be sensitive to outliers and multicollinearity. An alternative approach is to use a weighted method that can resist

the influence of outliers and multicollinearity. In the literature, several M-estimator-based approaches are available, but the redescending M-estimator is more resilient than M-estimator⁽¹¹⁾. Therefore, the aim is to enhance the ordinary LASSO method by incorporating this new weighting function, named the method Alarm Weight LASSO (AW-LASSO). The AW-LASSO is defined as follows.

$$\beta_{AW-LASSO} = \min_{\beta} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n w_i \left(y_i - \sum_j \beta_j X_{ij} \right)^2 + \lambda \sum_j |\beta_j| \right) \quad (2)$$

The w_i represents the weight of i^{th} observation. The weight function considered is from the redescending M-estimator⁽¹²⁾, which can deal with multicollinearity as well as the problem of an outlier to a greater extent than ordinary LASSO. The influence function is $\psi(k)$ and is defined as

$$\psi(k) = \begin{cases} \frac{16ke^{-2(k/c)^2}}{(1+e^{-(k/c)^2})^4} & , |k| \leq c \\ 0 & , |k| > c \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Integrating $\psi(k)$ function under the initial condition, the corresponding $\rho(k)$ is obtained and is given by

$$\rho(k) = \begin{cases} \frac{2c^2}{3} \left[1 - \frac{2(1+3e^{(k/c)^2})}{(1+e^{(k/c)^2})^3} \right] & , |k| \leq c \\ \frac{2c^2}{3} \left[1 - \frac{2(1+3e)}{(1+e)^3} \right] & , |k| > c \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The weight function $w(k) = \psi(k)/k$ and is given by

$$w(k) = \begin{cases} \frac{(4e^{-(k/c)^2})^2}{(1+e^{-(k/c)^2})^4} & , |k| \leq c \\ 0 & , |k| > c \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Where “ k ” represents the residual and “ c ” is the tuning constant. The weight function given in Equation (5) modifies the ordinary LASSO in Equation (1). The algorithm used to solve the proposed method is the same as that used to solve the ordinary LASSO method.

3 Measures of Multicollinearity

The correlation between the independent variables in the regression model is termed multicollinearity, which can affect the accuracy of the estimated model coefficients. The Common methods to detect the presence of multicollinearity in the regression model involve calculating the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) for individual predictors and analyzing the correlation matrix among predictors. In this paper the concept of VIF is used for checking multicollinearity and the method is explained by

The VIF is a measure of inflated variance in the estimated regression coefficients⁽¹²⁾. The general formula for VIF to the i^{th} predictor is

$$VIF_i = \frac{1}{1 - R_i^2} \quad (6)$$

The coefficient of determination is obtained by regressing X_i on the remaining predictor variables. VIFs are the diagonal elements of the inverse of the correlation matrix of the predictor variables. A widely accepted threshold for VIF is 10, then it is considered a problematic level of collinearity that has to be resolved⁽¹³⁾.

4 Results and Discussion

In this section, the performance of OLS-based LASSO introduced by Tibshirani⁽²⁾ and the proposed AW-LASSO method are compared in real and simulated settings. The performance of conventional LASSO and the proposed AW-LASSO method is studied in the presence of multicollinearity. The analysis is conducted using the R programming language. The results discuss the number of correctly and wrongly selected variables, as well as the Median Absolute Error (MDAE). The proposed method is useful wherever the dataset faces the problem of multicollinearity.

4.1 Real Data

This section presents the experimental results carried out under real data. The Abalone dataset is used to assess the performance of the proposed method in the presence of multicollinearity and it is obtained from the UC Irvine machine learning repository. The efficacy of the proposed method has been studied by considering the number of significant variables selected. The dataset contains information about the physical measurements of abalone shells, which can be used to predict the age of the abalone. It comprises 4177 observations with 7 predictor variables (Length, Diameter, Height, Whole Weight, Shucked Weight, Viscera Weight, Shell Weight) variables and 1 response variable. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Error-values and variables selected by each method in the presence of multicollinearity

Methods	MDAE	No. of Variables Selected	Variables Name
LASSO	0.383	6	Diameter, Height, Whole Weight, Shucked Weight, Viscera Weight, Shell Weight
AW-LASSO	0.393	4	Diameter, Height, Shucked Weight, Shell Weight

The Variables with a VIF greater than 10 are considered problematic. From the VIF analysis, it was found that except for Height, all other variables had a VIF greater than 10 (Height: 3.55, Length: 40.77, Diameter: 41.84, Whole Weight: 109.59, Shucked Weight: 28.35, Viscera Weight: 17.34, Shell Weight: 21.25). However, the correlation of residuals remained close to zero for both with and without Whole Weight in the model, suggesting little benefit from including it. The proposed method removed the variable, but the ordinary LASSO retained it. Removing Whole Weight revealed the following VIF values: Length: 42.86, Diameter: 44.88, Height: 3.11, Shucked Weight: 8.70, Viscera Weight: 11.02, and Shell Weight: 7.64. This indicates collinearity among Length, Diameter, and Viscera Weight. Both methods discarded Length, but the proposed method discarded Viscera Weight also, while the ordinary method retained it.

4.2 Simulation Study

The simulation aimed to study the effectiveness of modeling approaches. It involved different sample sizes (n = 100, 200, 1000) and three levels of correlation ($\rho = 0.96, 0.98, 0.999$) between the independent variables which indicates multicollinearity. When the correlation coefficient (ρ) exceeded 0.95, equation (6) experienced problematic collinearity, defined as exceeding 10. The covariates were generated from a multivariate normal distribution using the mvnorm function from the MASS package, with a mean vector $\mu = 0$ and covariance matrix $\Sigma = [\sigma_{ij} = \rho^{|i-j|}]$ in correlation form. The model included five significant variables, and the remaining is considered noise variables. The performance of the proposed method was compared with the ordinary method by considering whether the important variables were correctly identified in the presence of multicollinearity.

Table 2. Number of variables selected in the presence of multicollinearity

Method	n	Selected Variables	p = 10			p = 15			p = 20		
			ρ								
LASSO	100	Significant	5(2)	5(2)	3(3)	4(3)	4(2)	2(2)	5(4)	4(4)	3(3)
		(Insignificant)									
	200	MDAE	3.12	3.10	2.95	2.71	2.78	2.97	2.64	2.69	2.74
		Significant	5(3)	5(3)	3(3)	5(6)	5(5)	2(6)	5(5)	5(5)	1(7)
	1000	(Insignificant)									
		MDAE	2.82	2.82	2.84	2.57	2.58	2.63	2.65	2.66	2.70
100	Significant	5(1)	5(2)	4(2)	5(4)	5(4)	5(6)	5(5)	5(5)	5(7)	
	(Insignificant)										
AW-LASSO	100	MDAE	2.57	2.57	2.58	2.56	2.57	2.53	2.71	2.70	2.68
		Significant	5(2)	5(2)	3(3)	4(3)	4(2)	2(3)	5(4)	4(4)	3(3)
	200	(Insignificant)									
MDAE		3.04	3.03	3.12	3.29	3.35	3.35	2.99	3.10	3.09	
200	Significant	5(3)	5(3)	3(3)	5(6)	5(5)	1(7)	5(5)	5(5)	1(5)	
	(Insignificant)										
		MDAE	3.03	3.00	2.95	2.86	2.94	2.92	2.75	2.72	2.66

Continued on next page

Table 2 continued

1000	Significant (Insignificant)	5(0)	5(0)	4(2)	5(3)	5(3)	5(6)	5(3)	5(3)	5(6)
	MDAE	2.66	2.65	2.67	2.59	2.59	2.60	2.74	2.74	2.76

Table 2 shows that the ordinary LASSO selects a greater number of insignificant variables as the number of observations and the number of variables increases. The proposed AW-LASSO selects only a few insignificant variables when compared to the ordinary LASSO method.

5 Conclusion

The OLS-based LASSO finds it difficult to select the important variable in the case of multicollinearity. To overcome this problem, a method named AW-LASSO is proposed. The real data study based on the Abalone dataset shows that the ordinary LASSO retained the variable with the highest VIF in the model and also selected all the variables that are collinear with each other. In contrast, the proposed method shows better performance by effectively discarding unnecessary variables from the model. The simulation study also provides evidence that the proposed method performs well by selecting a smaller number of insignificant variables compared to the ordinary LASSO method. Thus, the AW-LASSO method acts as a robust approach for variable selection in regression models, particularly in scenarios involving multicollinearity.

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